

THERMOTOLERANCE IN COTTON: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ANTIOXIDANT GENE EXPRESSION UNDER HEAT STRESS

Shomakhmadov Shoakbar Shoazim o'g'li¹, Navruzov Sanjar Botirovich², Babayeva Dildora Tuygunovna³, Khashimova Nigora Rustamovna⁴, Akhunov Ali Akhunovich⁵

¹Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan Institute of Bioorganic chemistry named after A.S.Sadykov, junior researcher,

²Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan Institute of Bioorganic chemistry named after A.S.Sadykov, junior researcher,

³Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan Institute of Bioorganic chemistry named after A.S.Sadykov, senior researcher,

⁴Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan Institute of Bioorganic chemistry named after A.S.Sadykov, senior researcher,

⁵Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan Institute of Bioorganic chemistry named after A.S.Sadykov, professor.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15546193>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda paxtaning (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) uch xil navida — Ravnaq-2, Porloq-1 va Buxoro-102 — issiqlik stressi (45°C haroratda 6 soat) va tiklanish davrida asosiy antioksidant genlar — CAT1 (katalaza), POD (peroksidaza), SOD (superoksid dismutaza) va APX (askorbat peroksidaza) ekspressiyasi o'rganildi. Gen ekspressiyasi miqdoriy PZR (qPCR) usuli orqali $2^{(-\Delta\Delta Ct)}$ metodi asosida baholandi [8]. Issiqlik stressi ta'sirida barcha navlarda CAT1, POD va SOD genlari ekspressiyasi sezilarli darajada oshdi, APX geni ekspressiyasi esa kamaydi. 30°C da 6 soatlik tiklanish davrida aksariyat genlar ekspressiyasi dastlabki darajaga qaytdi, bu esa stress holati susayganini ko'rsatadi. Ayniqsa, Buxoro-102 navida CAT1 va SOD genlarining yuqori darajada faollashuvi kuzatildi, bu uning yuqori issiqlikka chidamliligidan dalolat beradi. Ushbu natijalar paxtaning issiqlikka chidamli navlarini aniqlashda antioksidant genlar ekspressiyasi profillaridan molekulyar marker sifatida foydalanish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: paxta (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.), issiqlik stressi, gen ekspressiyasi, qPCR, antioksidant genlar

Аннотация. В данном исследовании изучено экспрессирование ключевых антиоксидантных генов — CAT1 (каталаза), POD (пероксидаза), SOD (супероксиддисмутаза) и APX (аскорбатпероксидаза) — у трёх сортов хлопчатника (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.): Равнак-2, Порлок-1 и Бухоро-102 при тепловом стрессе (45°C в течение 6 часов) и последующем восстановлении. Экспрессия генов оценивалась методом количественной ПЦР (qPCR) с использованием метода $2^{(-\Delta\Delta Ct)}$ [8]. При тепловом стрессе уровни экспрессии CAT1, POD и SOD значительно увеличивались у всех сортов, тогда как экспрессия APX снижалась. В течение 6-часового периода восстановления при 30°C экспрессия большинства генов возвращалась к исходному уровню, что указывает на ослабление стрессового состояния. Особенно примечательно, что у сорта Бухоро-102 наблюдалась наибольшая индукция CAT1 и SOD, что свидетельствует о его высокой термоустойчивости. Полученные данные обеспечивают молекулярную основу для отбора

тепlostойких сортов хлопчатника на основе профилей экспрессии антиоксидантных генов.

Ключевые слова: хлопчатник (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.), тепловой стресс, экспрессия генов, qPCR, антиоксидантные гены

Abstract. This study investigated the expression of key antioxidant genes—CAT1 (catalase), POD (peroxidase), SOD (superoxide dismutase), and APX (ascorbate peroxidase)—in three cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) cultivars: Ravnaq-2, Porloq-1, and Buxoro-102, under heat stress (45°C for 6 hours) and a subsequent recovery period. Gene expression was assessed by quantitative PCR (qPCR) and analyzed using the $2^{-(\Delta\Delta Ct)}$ method [8]. Under heat stress, CAT1, POD, and SOD expression significantly increased in all cultivars, whereas APX expression declined. During the 6-hour recovery at 30°C, most gene expression levels returned toward baseline, indicating stress alleviation. Notably, Buxoro-102 exhibited the strongest induction of CAT1 and SOD, suggesting superior thermotolerance. These findings provide a molecular basis for selecting heat-tolerant cotton cultivars based on antioxidant gene expression profiles.

Keywords: cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.), heat stress, gene expression, qPCR, antioxidant genes.

Introduction

Cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) is a globally significant fiber and oil crop, contributing over 90% of the world's natural textile fibers and meeting the dietary oil needs of nearly half of the global population [1]. However, more than 50% of cotton cultivation areas worldwide are affected by abiotic stresses—such as salinity, drought, and extreme temperatures—which can severely reduce yield and fiber quality [2]. In particular, heat stress disrupts photosynthesis, enzyme function, and membrane stability, highlighting the need for developing heat-resilient cultivars [3,4].

Plants employ antioxidant enzymes to mitigate heat-induced oxidative stress. Catalase (CAT1) decomposes hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) into water and oxygen, reducing cellular damage. Peroxidase (POD) contributes to H₂O₂ detoxification and lignin biosynthesis, enhancing cell wall integrity. Superoxide dismutase (SOD) converts superoxide radicals into H₂O₂ and O₂, serving as a first line of defense against reactive oxygen species (ROS). Ascorbate peroxidase (APX) reduces H₂O₂ using ascorbate, thereby maintaining cellular redox homeostasis [5–7]. These antioxidant enzymes play pivotal roles in plant thermotolerance.

However, the specific expression responses of these antioxidant genes in different cotton cultivars under heat stress have not been characterized. In this study, we examined the expression profiles of CAT1, POD, SOD, and APX in the cotton cultivars Ravnaq-2, Porloq-1, and Buxoro-102 during heat stress and recovery. By comparing their gene expression patterns, we aim to identify cultivar-specific antioxidant responses and infer their relative thermotolerance.

Materials and Methods

Plant Material and Heat Stress Treatment

Three cotton cultivars—Ravnaq-2, Porloq-1, and Buxoro-102—were grown under controlled conditions (30°C; 16 h light/8 h dark photoperiod) for 21 days. Heat stress was applied by exposing plants to 45°C for 6 hours, followed by a 6-hour recovery period at 30°C. Leaf samples were collected immediately after the stress and recovery treatments, flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen, and stored at –80°C until RNA extraction.

RNA Isolation and cDNA Synthesis

Total RNA was extracted from leaf tissue (three biological replicates per cultivar) using the GeneJET Plant RNA Purification Kit (ThermoFisher Scientific, Cat. K0801). RNA quality and concentration were determined using a NanoDrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Cat. NDE-GL). First-strand cDNA was synthesized from 1 µg of total RNA using RevertAid Reverse Transcriptase (Evrogen, Cat. SK022S) following the manufacturer’s protocol.

Quantitative PCR and Gene Expression Analysis

Quantitative PCR (qPCR) was performed using SYBR Green I detection chemistry (50X SYBR Green I, Evrogen, Cat. PB025M) on a QuantStudio 5 Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems, Cat. A34322). Reaction mixtures contained Taq DNA polymerase (Invitrogen, Cat. 10966018), dNTPs, and gene-specific primers. Amplification conditions were: initial denaturation at 94°C for 5 min, followed by 45 cycles of 94°C for 15 s and 60°C for 30 s. Relative gene expression was calculated using the $2^{(-\Delta\Delta Ct)}$ method [8]. Data were reported as mean ± standard error (SE) from three biological replicates, and statistical analysis included calculation of standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation (CV%).

Results

Exposure to heat stress (45°C for 6 hours) significantly altered antioxidant gene expression in all three cotton cultivars. In general, CAT1, POD, and SOD transcripts were upregulated by heat, while APX transcripts were downregulated. During the 6-hour recovery period, the expression of most genes declined toward control levels, indicating stress alleviation. Based on the data presented in the following (diagram 1), the effects of high temperature stress on the expression of CAT1, POD, SOD, and APX genes in the cotton cultivars Ravnaq-2, Porloq-1, and Buxoro-102 are analyzed.

Diagram 1

Relative Gene Expression of Cotton Cultivars

- Optimal temperature
- Heat stress temperature
- Post-stress optimal temperature

CAT1: Under heat stress, CAT1 expression showed the strongest induction in Buxoro-102 (approximately 14.1-fold increase; +1311%), compared to only a 1.14-fold increase (+14%) in both Porloq-1 and Ravnaq-2. After recovery, CAT1 remained highly elevated in Buxoro-102 (~10.2-fold; +921%), whereas Porloq-1 and Ravnaq-2 returned near baseline. This pattern suggests that Buxoro-102 maintains a robust H₂O₂-detoxification response even after stress.

POD: Heat stress induced POD expression most strongly in Porloq-1 (1.63-fold; +63%), while POD levels were unchanged in Buxoro-102 and slightly decreased in Ravnaq-2 (0.93-fold; -7%). After recovery, POD expression dropped sharply in Buxoro-102 (to 0.47-fold; -53%) and in Ravnaq-2 (0.15-fold; -85%), but remained modestly elevated in Porloq-1 (1.12-fold; +12%). These results indicate that Porloq-1 mobilizes POD activity under heat stress and maintains it during recovery, whereas Buxoro-102 and Ravnaq-2 show much weaker POD induction.

SOD: Under heat stress, SOD expression was highest in Porloq-1 (4.58-fold; +358%), while Buxoro-102 and Ravnaq-2 showed only minor increases (~1.06-fold; +6% each). In all cultivars, SOD expression decreased during the recovery period. The strong SOD induction in Porloq-1 suggests an enhanced superoxide-scavenging capacity in this cultivar.

APX: In contrast to the other genes, APX expression was consistently downregulated by heat stress in all three cultivars. This may indicate a suppression of ascorbate-dependent H₂O₂ scavenging during acute heat stress, possibly as an energy-saving adaptation.

Discussion

Heat stress induced marked changes in antioxidant gene expression that varied by cultivar. The strong upregulation of CAT1 and SOD under heat stress indicates active ROS scavenging. Notably, the dramatic CAT1 induction in Buxoro-102 suggests a robust H₂O₂ detoxification capacity, consistent with previous findings that CAT1 is a major determinant of heat tolerance in cotton [9]. In contrast, Ravnaq-2 exhibited only minimal increases in CAT1 and SOD, indicating a weaker ROS defense response.

Porloq-1 displayed distinct patterns: significant induction of POD (during stress) and the highest SOD induction, implying enhanced cell wall reinforcement and superoxide scavenging. Its sustained POD expression during recovery suggests extended defense activation. Conversely, Ravnaq-2's slight POD decline and negligible SOD induction point to less effective antioxidant defenses.

The consistent downregulation of APX across all cultivars suggests that this pathway is deprioritized under acute heat stress, potentially reflecting limited ascorbate availability or an energy-saving response. Overall, these patterns imply that Buxoro-102 possesses the most effective antioxidant defense profile under heat stress, followed by Porloq-1, with Ravnaq-2 being least responsive.

Conclusion

Ravnaq-2: This cultivar showed only modest activation of antioxidant defenses. CAT1 and SOD were barely induced (~+14% and +6%, respectively), and POD expression even slightly declined under heat. The downregulation of APX alongside minimal changes in other enzymes suggests that Ravnaq-2 has limited capacity to detoxify H₂O₂ and superoxide during heat stress. These weak responses imply that Ravnaq-2 is the least thermotolerant of the three cultivars.

Porloq-1: Porloq-1 exhibited intermediate heat tolerance. It showed moderate CAT1 induction (similar to Ravnaq-2), but much higher POD (+63%) and especially SOD (+358%) induction. During recovery, POD remained slightly elevated and SOD declined but stayed above

control levels. These patterns suggest that Porloq-1 has enhanced superoxide scavenging and cell wall defense mechanisms, placing it between Ravnaq-2 and Buxoro-102 in thermotolerance.

Buxoro-102: Buxoro-102 demonstrated the strongest antioxidant response and inferred thermotolerance. Its CAT1 expression was induced by approximately 14-fold (+1311%) under heat, and remained highly elevated during recovery (+921%). SOD was slightly induced (+6%) and POD was unchanged, but the dominant CAT1 response indicates an exceptional capacity to decompose H₂O₂ generated during stress. The robust CAT1 (and sustained SOD) activity in Buxoro-102 suggests superior protection against heat-induced oxidative damage.

In summary, these cultivar-specific expression profiles indicate that Buxoro-102 is the most heat-tolerant, Porloq-1 has moderate tolerance, and Ravnaq-2 is the least tolerant. These findings provide a molecular basis for selecting heat-resilient *G. hirsutum* cultivars in breeding programs for arid environments.

REFERENCES

1. Zhang, J., et al. Cotton production in China: Achievements and challenges. *Crop Journal*, 2013. 1(4), p.251–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cj.2013.10.003>
2. Hasanuzzaman, M., et al. Physiological, biochemical, and molecular mechanisms of heat stress tolerance in plants. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 14(5), 2013. 9643–9684. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms14059643>
3. Reddy, K.R., et al. Physiological responses of cotton to heat stress and its mitigation strategies. *Advances in Agronomy*, 144, 2017. 1–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.agron.2017.02.001>
4. Bitá, C.E., & Gerats, T.. Plant tolerance to high temperature in a changing environment: Scientific fundamentals and production of heat stress-tolerant crops. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 4, 2013. 273. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2013.00273>
5. Gill, S.S., & Tuteja, N. Reactive oxygen species and antioxidant machinery in abiotic stress tolerance in crop plants. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*, 48(12), 2010. 909–930. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plaphy.2010.08.016>
6. Mittler, R. Oxidative stress, antioxidants and stress tolerance. *Trends in Plant Science*, 7(9), 2002. 405–410. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1360-1385\(02\)02312-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1360-1385(02)02312-9)
7. Apel, K., & Hirt, H. Reactive oxygen species: Metabolism, oxidative stress, and signal transduction. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 55, 2004. 373–399. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.arplant.55.031903.141701>
8. Livak, K.J., & Schmittgen, T.D. Analysis of relative gene expression data using real-time quantitative PCR and the 2^{-ΔΔCt} method. *Methods*, 25(4), 2001. 402–408. <https://doi.org/10.1006/meth.2001.1262>
9. Wahid, A., et al. Heat tolerance in plants: An overview. *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 61(3), 2007. 199–223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envexpbot.2007.05.011>